

PERIOPSIS

Climate-smart Forestry (CSF)

Building Resilience for Mediterranean Forests

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Training Overview

Module 1: Introduction to CSF and successful case studies

- Introduction to CSF
- Principles of CSF
- Forests as Carbon Sinks

Module 3: Climate change: Threats and Challenges to Mediterranean forests

- Anthropogenic Threats
- Biotic and Abiotic Hazards
- Vulnerability of Forests in Cyprus

Module 2: Mediterranean forests and their significance

- Mediterranean Forests' Characteristics
- Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
- Socioeconomic Importance of Mediterranean Forests

Module 4: CSF Application to Mediterranean forests

1. Implementing CSF Practices
2. Restoration Strategies Using Emerging Technologies
3. Stakeholder Engagement in CSF Decision-Making

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1. Introduction to CSF and successful case studies

Importance of Forests

- **Significant role in climate change mitigation** through capturing and storing CO₂ and helping regulate greenhouse gases.
- **Forests are under threat** by overgrazing, urban expansion, mining, land abandonment, subsistence or commercial use and other forms of deforestation.
- Deforestation and forest degradation contributes for approx. 20% of global GHG.

1. Introduction to CSF and successful case studies

What is Climate-Smart Forestry (CSF)?

CSF is a concept for policymakers and practitioners to set our governance and management strategies as a response to climate change.

It is aimed at:

- Enhancing **carbon sequestration**.
- Increasing **resilience** of forests to climate change.
- Ensuring **socio-economic benefits**.

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What is CSF?

Derived from the concept of Climate-Smart Agriculture, adapted to forestry in 2008.

CSF sets out actions in the following **three pillars**:

- **Mitigation**: Reducing or removing GHG emissions (e.g., carbon sequestration, storage).
- **Adaptation**: Increasing forest resilience to climate impacts (e.g., drought, pests).
- **Social Dimension**: Ensuring forests' productivity, income, and community benefits.

These actions can include **policy, planning** and forestry **practices**.

Source: Weatherall, A. *et al.* (2022). Defining Climate-Smart Forestry.

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Core Principles of CSF

- **Integration:** Mitigation, adaptation, and socio-economic dimensions must work together.
- **Multidisciplinary Approach:** Techniques for SFM that combine ecological, economic, and social sciences.
- **Ecosystem Services:** Focus on ecosystem resilience, forest productivity and stability with biodiversity conservation, water regulation and sustaining/highlighting cultural/social values.
- **Adaptive Management:** Dynamically respond to uncertain, changing conditions via monitoring and adjustments.

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Mitigation in CSF

Forest roles include:

Carbon Sequestration

Absorbing CO₂ via photosynthesis.

Carbon Storage

Long-term reservoirs in soil, vegetation, and biomass.

Carbon Substitution

Replacing high-carbon materials and fossil fuels with wood products and bioenergy.

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Adaptation in CSF

- Focuses on enhancing the capacity of forests to become more resilient and resistant to present and future climatic conditions, and overall to adapt to climate change.
- Enhanced by promoting genetic, compositional, structural, and functional diversity and stand and landscape levels.
 - **Facilitating natural regeneration** and planting native or non-native species that are more resilient to climate change.
 - **Increase forest connectivity** to assist species migration and ecosystem adaptation.
- Preparing forests for future climatic conditions.

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Social Dimension of CSF

Recognizing forests' connection to human well-being.

Emphasizing stakeholder engagement to resolve land-use conflicts and ensure equitable governance.

Supporting community priorities through ecosystem service assessments.

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Important!

CSF vs SFM: CSF doesn't replace **Sustainable Forest Management (SFM)** but optimizes climate benefits and synergies with other forest needs.

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Forests as Carbon Sinks

Forests mitigate climate change by:

- **Carbon Sequestration Science:** Forests absorb CO₂, storing it in biomass, vegetation, and soils.
- **Global Impact:** Forests offset ~2.6 billion tonnes of CO₂ each year (~1/3 of fossil fuel emissions; CIFOR 2017).
- **Regional Significance:** Mediterranean forests face water stress, limiting carbon absorption, and requiring targeted strategies and interventions.
- **Role in Climate Goals:** Crucial for achieving IPCC and Paris Agreement targets.
- Providing sustainable wood products that replace fossil fuel-intensive materials.

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CSF addresses these challenges by:

- Balancing timber production with conservation.
- Developing locally tailored solutions.

Criteria and Indicators (C&I)

- Used to monitor the progress and measure the benefits of the implementation of CSF policies and practices.
- CSF strategies vary by country based on:
 - Forest types and ecosystems.
 - Socio-economic and climatic challenges.

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